

GIS-Based Analysis and Prediction of Land Use and Land Cover Changes (LULCC) in Shkodra Region

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Abstract: Land cover changes are important indicators reflecting transformations in socio-economic and environmental conditions. This study analyzed the dynamics of land cover change in the Shkodra Region during the period 1991–2021 and assessed potential spatial changes for the year 2030 using Remote Sensing and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) technologies. Satellite imagery obtained from the USGS platform was used to identify the main land cover classes, including water bodies, built up areas, flood land, forests, agricultural land, mixed forests, shrubland and woody land. The results revealed significant transformations in land cover structure and land use patterns, closely associated with urbanization processes, infrastructure development, agricultural intensification, and increasing pressure on forest and wetland ecosystems. and use forecasting for 2030 was performed using the MOLUSCE plugin in QGIS, based on land cover transitions observed between 1991 and 2021, representing a 30-year calibration period. The year 2030 was selected as a medium term forecasting horizon to support regional spatial planning and sustainable environmental management strategies aligned with current territorial development objectives. The prediction model incorporated spatial variables such as slope, aspect, and distance from road networks to simulate future land cover transitions. The study highlighted the role of geospatial analysis in supporting decision-making for territorial planning and the sustainable management of natural resources in a region characterized by high morphological and hydrographic diversity, such as the Shkodra Region. The findings provide a scientific basis for the development of policies aimed at reducing environmental degradation and improving territorial sustainability.

Keywords: land cover; remote sensing; GIS; spatial modeling; MOLUSCE; land use forecasting.

1 Introduction

Land cover is defined as the physical and biophysical characteristics observed on the Earth's surface, representing the tangible description of spatial features (Di Gregorio and Jansen 1997). It includes categories such as vegetation (forests, shrubs, and grasslands), bare land, built-up surfaces, and water bodies. Land cover constitutes a fundamental component for the development of classification systems, spatial databases, and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), supporting the analysis of

spatial patterns and environmental dynamics. The assessment of land cover changes has become increasingly effective through the integration of Remote Sensing and GIS technologies, which enable the acquisition, processing, analysis, and visualization of geospatial information across different temporal scales.

Monitoring land cover dynamics is particularly important in regions characterized by high environmental diversity and increasing anthropogenic pressure. Changes in land cover are closely associated with processes such as urban expansion, agricultural intensification, infrastructure development, deforestation, and wetland degradation, all of which significantly influence ecosystem sustainability and territorial management. In this context, geospatial technologies provide valuable tools for identifying spatial transformations and supporting evidence-based decision-making for sustainable regional planning.

Shkodra Region is one of the largest and most geographically diverse regions in Albania, extending from the Albanian Alps in the north to the western coastal lowlands along the Adriatic Sea. The region is located approximately between 42°50' and 41°47' north latitude, and between 19°17' and 20°18' east longitude. Approximately 80% of its territory consists of mountainous terrain, while the highest elevation is represented by Mount Jezerca, reaching 2,694 m above sea level (AKT 2026). The region borders Montenegro to the north, Kukës Region to the east, Lezhë Region to the south, and the Adriatic Sea to the west.

One of the most important natural features of the region is Lake Shkodra, the largest lake in the Balkans, with a total surface area of approximately 368 km², of which 169 km² belong to Albanian territory, while the remaining area extends into Montenegro (Kraja and Albert 2026). The region also contains extensive wetlands, agricultural plains, forest ecosystems, and rapidly expanding urban areas, making it particularly sensitive to land cover transformations and environmental pressures.

This study aimed to analyze land cover changes during the period 1991–2021 using Remote Sensing and GIS techniques, as well as to model future land cover dynamics for the year 2030 through the use of the MOLUSCE plugin in QGIS. The selection of this region was related to the importance of the Shkodra Region from ecological, environmental, and spatial perspectives, as well as its specific territorial dynamics and development processes as the most important urban center in northern Albania.

For this reason, the study was structured mainly based on the methodological approach used for land cover classification and spatial modeling, followed by the discussion of the results of these changes and future spatial predictions. The research questions of this study focused on identifying the main land cover transformations in the Shkodra Region during the study period, determining the land cover classes that experienced the most significant spatial changes, analyzing current development trends, and exploring the potential evolution of land cover patterns by the year 2030.

Finally, the study concludes with the main findings and recommendations for sustainable territorial and environmental management.

2 Materials and methods

In this study, the application of Remote Sensing (RS) integrated with Geographic Information Systems (GIS) provides a comprehensive approach for analyzing land use/land cover (LULC) changes and their temporal dynamics. Remote Sensing enables the acquisition of accurate and up-to-date information on land characteristics, including vegetation cover, urban expansion, and forest changes, while GIS offers advanced tools for spatial data processing, analysis, and modeling. The integration of RS and GIS facilitates the examination of spatial relationships among environmental and socio-economic factors, enabling a more comprehensive assessment of LULC dynamics (Jensen 2015). Furthermore, GIS supports the integration of multiple spatial datasets, such as soil, climate, and vegetation data, and their representation through maps and spatial models, thereby improving the interpretation of spatial patterns and supporting informed decision-making for sustainable territorial planning.

For this study, satellite imagery from multiple years was acquired from the USGS EarthExplorer platform. Images were selected based on low cloud cover conditions (<10–20%) and consistent seasonal acquisition, specifically during July, in order to minimize phenological variability. In addition, Level-2 Surface Reflectance products were used because they include atmospheric correction processing, ensuring higher data quality and reliability for LULC change analysis (Table 1).

ArcGIS Pro software was used for satellite image processing, classification, and LULC change analysis. The

preparation of satellite data included band composition (layer stacking), clipping to the study area, and coordinate system standardization using the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection to ensure spatial consistency. The pre-processing phase was conducted in ArcGIS Pro and involved radiometric correction, atmospheric correction, and cloud masking procedures to ensure data quality and temporal comparability between datasets. The LULC classification process was performed using the Support Vector Machine (SVM) supervised classification algorithm based on training samples representing the main LULC classes in the study area. The application of the SVM algorithm enabled the generation of LULC maps for the years 1991, 2001, and 2021. The use of SVM was selected due to its high classification accuracy and strong performance in handling complex and heterogeneous landscapes commonly found in the Shkodra region.

In this study, the prediction of future LULC changes was conducted through an integrated modeling approach within the QGIS platform using the MOLUSCE (Modules for Land Use Change Simulation) plugin (QGIS Development Team 2023, NextGIS 2015). The modeling process was based on the analysis of changes identified between the 2001 and 2021 LULC maps, which were used respectively as the initial state (T1) and final state (T2) for the transition potential model. These years were selected because they represent a sufficiently long temporal interval to capture significant land use dynamics and urban expansion trends in the study area. Based on these historical dynamics, the year 2030 was selected as the target projection year in order to support future territorial planning and sustainable resource management strategies.

The classified LULC maps and relevant driving factors (distance to roads, topography, existing land use) are incorporated into MOLUSCE to develop a transition potential model.

The modeling process employed an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) algorithm to identify relationships between spatial variables and the probability of transition from one LULC class to another. Subsequently, the ANN model was integrated with a Cellular Automata (CA) approach to simulate the spatial allocation of future changes while accounting for neighborhood effects and spatial structure (Shafizadeh-Moghadam et al. 2017).

The final output is a projected LULC map for 2030, reflecting trends and spatial dynamics of the study area.

Table 1. Data Sources.

Data	Source	Resolution	Year	Description	Type of Data
DEM	USGS	30 m	2018	SRTM 30	Tiff
Satellite imagery	USGS	30 m	1991	Landsat 5, TM Sensor	Tiff
Satellite imagery	USGS	30 m	2001	Landsat 7, ETM+ Sensor	Tiff
Satellite imagery	USGS	30 m	2021	Landsat 8,9, OLI/TIRS Sensor	Tiff
Road and Infrastructure	OSM				Shape File

This approach provides a framework for scenario analysis supporting informed decision making in spatial planning and sustainable resource management.

3 Land Cover Changes (1991–2021)

Land cover maps for the study area over the period 1991–2021 were classified into nine main categories, including water bodies, built up areas, flood land, forests, agricultural land, mixed forests, shrubland, and woody land (Figure 1). A comparative analysis for the years 1991, 2001, and 2021 reveals significant changes, with agricultural, forest, and developed areas representing the dominant land use categories in the Shkodra region.

The results shown in table 2 indicate an increase in developed areas, bare land, and water bodies, while agricultural, forest, and wetland areas have declined, specifically by 3.07%, 14.01%, and 0.94%, respectively. These trends reflect substantial transformations in land use and increasing pressure on natural resources over the past three decades.

Water bodies showed a gradual decrease throughout the study period, declining from approximately 30% in 1991 and 2001 to less than 29% in 2021, representing an overall reduction of about 1–2% over the three decades.

Built-up areas experienced the most significant growth, increasing from approximately 15% in 1991 to nearly 20% in 2001, and reaching almost 38% in 2021. This indicates an increase of around 5% during 1991–2001 and nearly 18% during 2001–2021, with a total growth of about 23% over the entire study period.

Figure 1. (a) Land Cover 1991 (b) Land Cover 2001 (c) Land Cover 2021 (d) Land Cover Prediction 2030.

Flood-prone land showed a fluctuating trend, decreasing from around 25% in 1991 to 20% in 2001, corresponding to a reduction of approximately 5%. However, by 2021, this class increased again to nearly 23%, reflecting a recovery of about 3% compared to 2001, although it still remained lower than its 1991 extent by approximately 2%.

Table 2. Land Cover Change Detection (1991–2021).

	Surface % (1991)	Surface % (2001)	Surface % (2021)
Water	30.09667	30.08859	29.008567
Build Up	15.0416	18.07901	38.04439
Flood-prone	25.51364	20.54286	23.118511
Dense	14.47882	14.91235	5.37262
Agricultural	7.571963	7.919326	3.293741
Mixed	3.952931	4.919622	0.830984
Shrubland	0.972076	0.972076	0.760846
Forest	0.490077	0.694725	0.00011
Wood land	1.152489	1.141719	0.67023
Other	0.73	0.74	0

Land cover changes have been driven by the interaction of physical and socio-economic factors. Lowland areas with gentle slopes, particularly in the western part of the region, have experienced the most pronounced transformations, whereas mountainous and forested areas in the north and east have remained relatively stable.

4 Discussion

This study identified significant land use/land cover (LULC) changes in the Shkodra region during the period 1991–2021. The expansion of built-up areas, which increased by approximately 23%, reflects rapid urban growth and increasing pressure for territorial development. As a consequence, agricultural and forested areas declined, leading to a gradual transformation of natural and productive land into residential, industrial, and infrastructure-related areas. Meanwhile, water bodies and flood-prone areas experienced relatively minor changes during the study period.

Similar studies conducted in Albania and the Western Balkans also emphasize the important role of urbanization and infrastructure development in landscape transformation and land use change, identifying them as major factors contributing to the loss of natural and agricultural land. The CA-ANN model used for predicting land use changes for the year 2030 achieved satisfactory validation results, with an overall accuracy of 82.43% and a Kappa coefficient of 0.72. The projected scenario suggests a further increase in built-up areas (+5.12%) and a continuous decline in agricultural land (−3.73%) and forest areas (−1.09%).

Considering the spatial resolution of Landsat imagery, possible classification errors, and the limitations of the CA-ANN modeling approach itself, a certain level of uncertainty remains within the methodological application. In addition, influencing factors such as population growth, urbanization, and economic development were not directly analyzed in this study through statistical or socio-

economic data. This is particularly relevant in urban areas characterized by fragmented development patterns or in territories with complex interconnections between land cover classes. As a result, some small-scale local changes may not have been fully captured in the classification and modeling results.

5 Conclusions

This study highlighted the significant increase in built-up areas and the gradual decline of agricultural and forest land, particularly in lowland and peri-urban areas.

The results of the future land use modeling for the year 2030 indicate that the trend of urban expansion is expected to continue, creating new challenges for the protection of natural resources, agricultural land, and forest areas, as well as for the sustainable management of the territory. The integration of Remote Sensing, GIS, and CA-ANN modeling proved to be a valuable approach for analyzing spatial dynamics and supporting territorial planning in the Shkodra region. The main objective of this study was precisely to provide such a methodological framework as a useful tool for scientific research focused on territorial analysis and regional development.

For future studies, it remains important to integrate socio-economic and demographic indicators into the research framework, as these factors may contribute to a more accurate interpretation of the processes influencing

landscape change and the spatial development of the region.

6 References

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